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Effect of Fuel Injection Pressure Variations on Engine Performance-Emission-Particulate Matter with Diesel-Iso-Butanol-Nanoparticle Fuels in Compression Ignition Engine

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Abstract

Background/Objective: Growing environmental concerns and the depletion of petroleum supplies have generated a lot of interest in alternate fuels. Made from renewable resources, biodiesel is one of the many useful and advantageous fuel alternatives to fossil fuels. The use of nanoparticles as fuel additives for internal combustion engines is now possible because to recent developments in nanotechnology. Previous research indicated that these substances could improve engine performance. This could lead to an increase in particulate matter released with the exhaust, which would have a negative impact on the quality of the air. This study investigates engine performance, emission properties, and size distribution of unregulated particulate matter (PM) released with exhaust gases. **Methods:** In this work, iso-butanol is proposed to be blended with Diesel along with aluminum oxide as a nano-additive 100 mg/L using Mechanical String method for 1 hour. Engine testing is conducted at fuel injection pressures of 180, 210, and 240 bar. To examine the performance, emission characteristics and particulate matter, a 4-stroke, single cylinder, direct-injection, 5-horsepower (3.5 kW) research Diesel engine was selected having a mass flow sensor, burette method, a dynamometer computerised data gathering system, a variety of sensors were used in the experiment to gather, store, and evaluate data (Internal Combustion engine software). **Findings:** Results indicated that blend B20 gives better results compare to other blends (B10, B30 and B40). In comparison to pure diesel fuel, the diesel/biodiesel blend combination produced 10–15 % less PM1, PM2.5, the Maximum brake thermal efficiency of Diesel(31.46 %), 180 bar(28.56 %), 210 bar(29.45 %), 240 bar (30.14 %). The maximum brake specific fuel consumption of Diesel(0.28 kg/kw-hr), 180bar(0.32 kg/kw-hr), 210 bar(0.31 kg/kw-hr), 240

bar(0.30 kg/kw-hr). The maximum of CO Diesel(0.22 %/vol), 180 bar (0.18 %/vol), 210 bar(0.14 %/vol), 240 bar(0.12 %of vol) as comparative of above values the blend B20 and injection pressure of 240bar shows similar to Diesel. **Novelty:** This study compares diesel and treated bio-diesel at different parameters: fuel injection pressures, break thermal efficiency, mechanical efficiency, and CO, HC, opacity, and particle matter.

Keywords: Iso-butanol; Aluminum oxide; Fuel injection pressure; Engine performance; Emission characteristics

1 Introduction

Utilizing Bio-Diesel, a sustainable fuel, can reduce the use of petroleum-based fuels and, consequently, the overall greenhouse gas emissions from internal combustion engines⁽¹⁾. BioDiesel's better physio-chemical qualities, renewable nature, non-toxicity, low sulfur content, environmental friendliness, and increased oxygen content make it ethically acceptable among the various alternatives (vegetable oils)⁽²⁾. However, the commercialization of Bio-Diesel is hindered by a number of factors, including poor performance, poor oxidation stability, increased NOx emissions, piston sticking concerns, and the absence of cold flow parameters (cloud point (CP) and pour point (PP)). Fuel blending is also influenced by fuel prices; TiO₂, CeO₂, GO, and CNT are a few of the priciest nanoparticles⁽³⁾. Due to these limitations, several tactics were developed, including the addition of alcohols and nanoparticles as additives to enhance performance, physico-chemical properties, and combustion parameters while reducing pollutants. Since Bio-Diesel-Diesel blends can now replace Diesel fuel, it has become increasingly customary to include various additives⁽⁴⁾. With their increased surface-to-volume ratio and thermal conductivity, the nanoparticles act as a catalyst to enhance the engine's physiochemical characteristics, boost overall performance, and cut emissions⁽⁴⁾. Iso-butanol, on the other hand, has better qualities and more energy than ethanol, methanol, and n-butanol, making it a viable alcohol additive. Butanol has an isomer called iso-butanol. Consequently, n-butanol and iso-butanol are members of the same family, but they have different chemical structures and the same molecular weight. The high energy level of the long-chain iso-butanol addition makes it simple to incorporate into Bio-Diesel-Diesel mixes⁽⁵⁾. Due mainly to its beneficial properties, biobutanol is emerging as a viable alternative biofuel to address the problems. These include having a higher density and energy content than conventional biofuels, as well as being able to blend well with gasoline, which increases its potential as a replacement⁽⁶⁾. The production of biobutanol, also known as iso-butanol, from biomass is a practical way to achieve carbon neutrality, lessen dependency on fossil fuels, and make use of sustainable and renewable resources. The lignocellulosic materials are widely acknowledged as excellent feedstocks for butanol production. After a series of steps, including initial pretreatment, fermentation, and iso-butanol production, different biomass feedstocks are converted into iso-butanol⁽⁷⁾.

By integrating nanoparticles into the blends of biobutanol & Diesel, the combustion properties could be enhanced. The concentration of fuel additives ranges from a few PPM to a thousand PPM. Certain nanoparticles carry out corrosion resistance and antioxidant properties, while others might facilitate seamless fuel flow⁽⁶⁾. Cerium (Ce), cerium-iron (Ce-Fe), platinum (Pt), CuO, CuCl₂, COCl₂, FeCl₂, Al₂O₃, multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNT), MgO, SiO₂, and other metal-based nanoparticles are employed in Bio-Diesel to enhance its viscosity, density, and flow characteristics. The effectiveness of the stated nanoparticles has been demonstrated by numerous researches⁽⁸⁾. Along with performance of Diesel engines is influenced by fuel injection pressure. Fuel particle diameter is reduced by increased injection pressure. This leads

to greater performance characteristics, improved combustion, and better fuel-air mixes⁽⁹⁾. It is possible to achieve lean combustion, better fuel atomization and evaporation, and decreased emissions by using high pressure injection with small orifices⁽¹⁰⁾. According to recent studies, additives are becoming essential instruments for performance optimization and cutting down on engine pollution⁽¹¹⁾. Particularly, it has been demonstrated that oxygenates such as ethanol, isopropanol, iso-butanol, and isopentanol enhance important performance metrics and dramatically lower particulate matter^(12,13). In⁽¹⁴⁾, studied the performance, combustion and emission reduction characteristics of Metal-based silicon dioxide nanoparticle additives included in ternary fuel (Diesel-SMME-iso butanol) on Diesel engine. Generally, in the previous studies, the fuel injection parameters were not considered. The current manuscript examines the fuel injection pressure of performance, emission characteristics, and particulate matter on an iso-butanol and aluminum oxide blend.

Particulate Matter:

Particulate matter (PM) is a complex mixture of liquid droplets and small solid particles that are suspended in the atmosphere. These particles are usually categorized by their aerodynamic diameter and vary in size, content, and origin. PM_{2.5}, which is especially concerning because of its capacity to enter the bloodstream and penetrate deeply into the respiratory system, and PM₁₀, which are particles with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or less, are the two most frequently researched categories.

1. Natural Resources:

- Wildfires: Wildfires greatly raise PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels by releasing copious volumes of smoke and ash into the atmosphere.
- Dust Storms: In arid and semi-arid areas, wind-induced soil erosion can raise dust particles into the atmosphere, resulting in bigger PM₁₀ particles.
- Volcanic eruptions: Both PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} are produced when volcanic activity releases gasses and fine particles.

2. Human-Made Sources:

- Vehicle Emissions: One of the main sources of primary and secondary particulate matter, particularly PM_{2.5}, is the exhaust from automobiles, trucks, and industrial vehicles.
- Industrial Processes: Particulate matter is released by factories, refineries, and power plants during combustion and other production operations.
- Construction Activities: A lot of dust and fine particles are produced by mining, road construction, and demolition.

Justification for Adding Nanoparticles

- Nanoparticles, such as Al₂O₃, are added to fuel blends to enhance combustion efficiency and reduce emissions.
- They improve the physical properties of the fuel, such as viscosity and surface tension, leading to better atomization.
- Nanoparticles can also promote more complete combustion by increasing the thermal conductivity of the fuel, which helps in heat transfer during combustion.

Impact of Fuel Injection Pressure

- Atomization and Mixing: Higher fuel injection pressures lead to finer atomization of fuel droplets, improving the mixing of fuel and air.
- Combustion Timing: Increased injection pressure can advance the start of combustion, leading to a more complete combustion process.
- Combustion Duration: Higher pressures can shorten the combustion duration, reducing the likelihood of incomplete combustion and soot formation.

Nomenclature

- TiO₂ Titanium dioxide
- CeO₂ Cerium oxide
- PPM Parts per million
- CuO Copper Oxide
- CuCl₂ Copper(II) chloride
- MgO Magnesium oxide

- SiO₂ Silicon Dioxide
- COCl₂ Phosgene
- FeCl₂ Iron(II) Chloride

2 Methodology

Fig 1. Methodology

2.1 Production of Iso-butanol

The production process of isobutanol from lignocellulosic biomass, divided into five main stages: **Lignocellulosic Biomass** (e.g., corn stover or sugarcane bagasse) → **Processing** → **Pretreatment** → **Hydrolysis** → **Fermentation** → **Product Recovery** → **Isobutanol**.

1. **Processing:** Biomass undergoes drying and milling to prepare it for further steps.
2. **Pretreatment:** The processed biomass is treated with acid or alkali to break down its structure.
3. **Hydrolysis:** Enzymes are added to convert the pretreated material into fermentable sugars.
4. **Fermentation:** Microorganisms ferment the sugars to produce isobutanol.
5. **Product Recovery:** Isobutanol is extracted and purified using methods such as distillation, pervaporation, and gas stripping.

This process integrates chemical and biochemical techniques to convert renewable plant-based materials into a valuable product, reducing reliance on fossil fuels.

Fig 2. Isobutanol Production

2.2 Iso-butanol

Iso-butanol is among the next generation of biofuels. The chemical industry uses iso-butanol, also known as 2-methyl-1-propanol, a four-carbon alcohol with a branched structure, extensively as a platform product. At 20 °C, iso-butanol has a relative density of 0.802, a melting point of -108 °C, and a boiling point of 108 °C. At 25 °C, iso-butanol has a vapour pressure of 10.43 mm Hg, or 13.9 hPa, and a solubility of 85 g/L in pure water.

2.3 Aluminum Oxide Al_2O_3 (Nanoparticle)

One of the nanoparticles found in metals is aluminum oxide. Al_2O_3 is the chemical symbol for it. Every time, alumina proved to be a superior oxidation catalyst. Because of its high tensile strength, excellent tear resistance, biocompatibility, high strength, and high heat conductivity, it is used extensively. About 3987 kg/m³ is its density. 2,977°C is the boiling point, and 2072°C is the melting point.

2.4 Mechanical Pressure-Regulating Valves in Diesel Engines

Mechanical pressure-regulating valves are commonly used in older or simpler Diesel fuel systems. They operate using a spring-loaded diaphragm or piston to control fuel pressure. When fuel pressure exceeds a set threshold, the spring compresses, opening a passage for excess fuel to return to the tank. Once the pressure drops, the spring pushes the valve closed, maintaining the desired pressure. These valves are straight forward and rely purely on mechanical components, requiring no electronic controls. The pressure threshold is determined by the spring's tension, which can sometimes be adjusted. They are durable and reliable but lack the precision of modern electronic pressure-regulating systems. Mechanical valves are susceptible to wear, such as spring fatigue or clogging from contaminated fuel. They are ideal for applications requiring simplicity and robustness.

2.5 Blend Preparation and Properties

Iso-butanol (IB) is used to create the biofuel for this experiment, and Diesel is combined with aluminium oxide in different amounts to create B10, B20, B30, and B40, among other mixtures.

- B10 Blend (90D + 10IB + 100mg/L Al_2O_3),
- B20 Blend (80D + 20IB + 100mg/L Al_2O_3),
- B30 Blend (70D + 30IB + 100mg/L Al_2O_3),
- B40 Blend (60D + 40IB + 100mg/L Al_2O_3).

Fig 3. Blending of Nano Fuel

Fig 4. Fuel injection timing

Table 1. Properties of Blend Samples of Diesel, B10, B20, B30 and B40

Sample	Units	Diesel	B10	B20	B30	B40
Density	kg/m ³	821	818	817	810	806
Calorific value	kJ/kg	45448	44266	43611	43099	41457
Flash point	°C	53	46	40	38	35
Fire point 2,Trimethyl-1,2-Dihydroquinoline)	°C	56	48	44	42	38
Dynamic viscosity	cP	1.73	2.13	2.04	1.97	1.8

Fig 5. Blend Samples

2.6 Experimental set-up

To examine the performance and emission characteristics, a 4-stroke, direct-injection, 5-horsepower (3.7 KW) research Diesel engine was selected (Figure 6). A mass flow sensor was used to monitor the engine’s air flow rate, while the burette method was used to measure the fuel consumption.

A dynamometer that measures eddy current was used to apply load to the engine. At various loads, the experiment was conducted (0, 25, 50, 75 % and full load). Using a computerised data gathering system, a variety of sensors were used in the experiment to gather, store, and evaluate data (IC engine software). To measure the emissions of O₂, HC, CO, CO₂, and NO_x, an exhaust gas analyzer (Airrex HG-540, 5Gas analyzer) was used. The results of the performance, combustion, and emission tests were tallied. Table 2 displays the details of the research engine.

Fig 6. Experimental Setup

Table 2. Specification of Test Rig

SPECIFICATION	TYPE
Type	Kirloskar
Stroke	4

Continued on next page

Table 2 continued

Power	3.70 Kw
Rated speed	1500 RPM
Cylinders	Single Cylinder Engine
Type of Cooling	Forced Circulated water-cooled system
Type of Engine	Compression-Ignition Diesel Engine
Cylinder bore	80.00mm
Stroke length	110mm
Compression ratio (CR)	18
Length of Connecting Rod	234mm
Loading device	Eddy current Dynamometer
Temperature sensor	Thermocouple

3 Results and Discussion

We examine the engine’s performance and emission characteristics when using Bio-Diesel (iso-butanol + Al₂O₃). An analysis and study were conducted on the engine performance and emission characteristics of various blends.

3.1 Load V/S Break Thermal Efficiency (BTHE)

Diesel consistently outperforms all Bio-Diesel blends across both pressure conditions (180 bar and 210 bar) and at all loads. B10 performs relatively well at low loads but declines at higher loads. B20 is the most efficient Bio-Diesel blend overall, especially at higher loads. B40 generally shows the lowest efficiency, particularly at higher loads and pressures. It was found that the maximum brake thermal efficiency at peak loads of 240 bar of the B20 blend is 27.96%; at 210 bar, the BTH is 26.55; and 25.44% of brake thermal efficiency is obtained at 180 bar compared to Diesel brake thermal efficiency, which is 28.45%. By the above values, it is stated that the brake thermal efficiency of Diesel engines and B20 (80% Diesel + 20% iso-butanol + 100 mg/L of Al₂O₃) blends at 240 bar shows similar results. 100 mg/L Al₂O₃ improves BTHE values primarily at higher loads compared to lower loads. This results from the atomization of fuel droplets brought on by higher fuel injection pressures, which also ensures that there is enough oxygen present in the combustion chamber. However, the BTH is lower for B30 and B40 due to the Bio-Diesel blend’s decreased density.

Fig 7. Load V/S Brake Thermal Efficiency

3.2 Load V/S Mechanical Efficiency

The mechanical efficiency fluctuation with regard to load and fuel injection pressures is depicted in Figure 8, based on the analysis of the experimentation.

3.2.1 Pressure Effect (180 bar vs 210 bar vs 240 bar):

For each fuel type (Diesel, B10, B20, B30, B40), as the pressure increases from 180 bar to 240 bar, mechanical efficiency also tends to increase. This suggests that the engine is operating more efficiently at higher pressures across all fuel types.

3.2.2 Fuel Type Effect (Diesel vs B10, B20, B30, B40):

- **Diesel Fuel:** Diesel shows the highest efficiency across all pressures and loads. It maintains relatively consistent increases in efficiency as load increases.
- **B10 to B40:** As the %age of Bio-Diesel increases, the mechanical efficiency generally decreases compared to Diesel, especially at lower loads (0% and 3%). However, for higher loads (9% and 12%), some of the Bio-Diesel blends like B30 and B40 approach or match the efficiency of Diesel, especially at higher pressures (240 bar).

3.2.3 Load Effect:

Efficiency increases with load: For all fuel types and pressures, mechanical efficiency increases with load, which is expected as the engine is operating closer to its full capacity. However, the rate of increase can vary depending on the fuel type and pressure. The highest mechanical efficiency at 180 Bar B30 is 49.86 %. The graph deduces that the maximum mechanical efficiency is 43.36 % at 210 Bar B30. The data shows that the highest mechanical efficiency at 240 Bar B20 is 52.53 %. The oxygen content of iso-butanol is larger (21.62 %) than that of normal Diesel due to its cetane number of 25. The mechanical efficiency of B20 is found to be higher than that of B10 due to the increased %age of iso-butanol in B20 than B10, and also the addition of aluminum oxide also cause the increase the combustion temperature and the self-ignition temperature of B20 Bio-Diesel is lower than that of the B10 blend.

Fig 8. Load V/S Mechanical Efficiency

3.3 Load V/S Brake Specific Fuel Consumption (BSFC)

The fluctuation of brake-specific fuel consumption is displayed in Figure 9 based on the load vs. brake-specific fuel consumption study.

BSFC at 0 % Load:

- For 180 bar, the BSFC for Diesel remains at 3.8 kg/kw-hr, while for B10+50gm/l of Al₂O₃, it is 5.1 kg/kw-hr, showing that the addition of Al₂O₃ increases the BSFC.
- For B20, B30, and B40, the BSFC values are also slightly higher than Diesel at 0 % load. This suggests that adding Al₂O₃ results in an increase in fuel consumption for these Bio-Diesel blends.
- At 240 bar, the BSFC for B40+50gm/l of Al₂O₃ is lower (3.11 kg/kw-hr), indicating that higher pressure may help reduce BSFC even when adding the additive.

BSFC at Higher Loads (3%, 6%, 9%, 12%):

- Diesel shows a consistent trend of decreasing BSFC as load increases, which is typical.
- B10 with 50g/l of Al₂O₃ exhibits higher BSFC at all loads compared to Diesel, especially noticeable at 3% and 6% load.
- B20 with 50g/l of Al₂O₃ also tends to have slightly higher BSFC than Diesel, but the difference decreases as load increases.
- B30 and B40 with 50g/l of Al₂O₃ show mixed results, with some instances where they approach or match the efficiency of Diesel, particularly at higher pressures (240 bar).

Effect of Pressure on BSFC:

- **BSFC decreases** as pressure increases for most fuel types, indicating that the engine operates more efficiently at higher pressures.
- **Al₂O₃ additives** still result in increased fuel consumption compared to pure Diesel, but this effect is less pronounced at higher pressures. The study finds that, when compared to other blends, blend B20 provides the best brake-specific fuel consumption (0.30) at 240 bar. This is because improved fuel alienation (Al₂O₃ + Iso-butanol) at greater injection pressures results in sharper fuel, which improves mix in the combustion chamber and reduces brake-specific fuel consumption. The length of the injection is also reduced by the rise in injection pressure. Injecting less fuel results in better air-fuel mixing and more premixed heat release.

Fig 9. Load V/S Brake-Specific Fuel Consumption

3.4 Load V/S CO

Poor air entrainment, insufficient oxygen content, rich mixes, inadequate mixture preparation, and incomplete combustion are the main causes of carbon monoxide (CO) emissions.

Figure 10 illustrate how CO varies in relation to loading and fuel injection pressures. Based on the data, BioDiesel blends (especially B10 and B20) generally reduce CO emissions compared to Diesel, particularly at higher injection pressures and

lower loads. Higher injection pressures (240 bar) improve the combustion process, reducing CO for all fuels, with B20 showing particularly good performance. B40 and higher blends might produce more CO under certain conditions due to challenges in atomization and combustion efficiency. the CO value obtained is 0.07 at 180 Bar B20. The graph deduces that the CO is 0.05 at 210 Bar B20. The data, which indicates that the CO is 0.06 at 240 Bar B20. This is because there is oxygen in iso-butanol itself. Lower CO emissions could result from employing this strategy.

Fig 10. Load V/S Carbon Monoxide

3.5 LOAD V/S HC

Fuel residue is contained in hydrocarbon (HC) emissions, which serve as a helpful indicator of inefficient combustion. About 98 % of the air-fuel mixture may usually be converted into combustion products by C.I. engines. Because they consistently run with overall lean fuel-air equivalency ratios, it is discovered that the HC emissions are decreased. Since the flame does not spread into these regions, the presence of gaseous hydrocarbons in the crevice's sections and the cylinder wall's significantly the main factors for HC emissions are boundary layers with lower temperatures.

Figure 11 illustrate the variance of HC with regard to load and fuel injection pressures. B10 and B20: Generally reduce HC emissions at low loads and perform better than Diesel, especially at higher injection pressures (240 bar). B30 and B40: Show significantly higher HC emissions due to incomplete combustion, particularly at light loads and lower injection pressures. 240 Bar Injection Pressure: Demonstrates the most effective reduction in HC emissions for all fuels, with better atomization and combustion efficiency. Hydrocarbon emissions are decreased by 26.66 % at injection pressures of 180–240 bar during peak loads. It has been discovered that when brake power rises, the %age of HC decreases due to complete burning of the fuel particles.

3.6 LOAD V/S NOx

Nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) are the two most common categories for the oxides of nitrogen emissions (NO_x). The combustion product known as NOx emission is made up of 10–30% NO₂ and the residual NO. Within the engine cylinder, nitric oxide is created and is a crucial component of the oxides of nitrogen. At a temperature of 2200 K, oxidation occurs inside the engine cylinder, producing oxides of nitrogen emissions. It takes a lot of energy for nitrogen to break its triple bond. Emissions of NO_x occur when the high combustion temperature promotes oxidation. The temperature at which the cylinder burns and the amount of oxygen present determine whether NO_x emissions develop. Compression ignition engines produce more NO_x emissions and always operate with lean air-fuel mixes.

Fig 11. Load V/S Hydrocarbons

Figure 12 show how different blends’ oxide of nitrogen emissions change with load in response to different fuel injection pressures (180, 210, and 240 bar). The figure shows that when the load increases, so do the engine’s nitrogen oxide emissions, and when the blend % increases, so do the emissions of NO_x . The NO_x content does, however, decrease at peak load at blend B40. Mixing B40 at 180 bar results in 693 PPM, while blending at 476 PPM. B40 at 240 bar. The NO_x emission rises in tandem with the load and mix %.

Fig 12. Load V/S Oxides of Nitrogen

3.7 Opacity

Soot refers to the fine particulate matter, primarily composed of carbon, produced by incomplete combustion of fuel in an engine. It is a solid substance that can be seen as black particles or smoke. Diesel produces high opacity, and pressure has no effect on emissions. BioDiesel blends (B10, B20, B30, B40) show consistently lower opacity (emissions) than Diesel, suggesting these blends are cleaner. For B10, B20, and B30, the opacity fluctuates with pressure, but higher pressures (240 bar) can sometimes result in lower opacity. B20 remains stable with low opacity, indicating it might be the most effective Bio-Diesel blend for reducing emissions. This can be achieved by Iso-butanol is an alcohol-based fuel and has a significantly lower aromatic content than traditional Diesel. Aromatics are known to contribute to the formation of particulate matter. The absence of aromatic compounds in iso-butanol reduces soot formation and, consequently, opacity.

Fig 13. Load V/S Opacity

3.8 Particulate matter (PM)

When compared to earlier, 240 bar offers improved performance and emission characteristics. Figure 14 shows the PM emissions for the diesel engine utilizing various fuel blends with aluminum oxide at 240 bar. The study examines the particulate matter emissions of diesel fuel and biodiesel made from iso-butanol blends at 240 bar and shows them in relation to engine output power.

It showed that, in contrast to D100, the B10 blend mix generated more emissions of particulate matter (PM-2.5 and PM-10). Being an oxygen-containing substance, aluminum oxide or iso-butanol may increase the amount of oxygen that can burn, lessen localized anoxic conditions inside the cylinder, and prevent the formation of soot. Additionally, the nanoparticle molecule's C–O bond has a greater bond energy, which lowers the generation of soot and soot precursors and hence reduces emissions of soot. Due to the micro-explosions, the mix fuel droplets continue to shrink until they burn entirely. By reducing particulate matter size without compromising combustion efficiency, the micro explosions enable the smaller fuel particles to more readily contact with air and complete combustion.

For example at the lowest power output of 0.14 kW, for PM 1.0, the Aluminum oxide nanoparticles reduced the PM from 0.05 for diesel fuel case and 0.041 for diesel/biodiesel. For PM10.0, it dropped from 0.45 for diesel or 0.40 for diesel/biodiesel to about 0.35 mg/l for Aluminum oxide. Diesel, iso-butanol and Aluminum oxide nanoparticles together might be a more effective way to inhibit elemental carbon synthesis and reduce particulate matter pollution. Because of the at least 100 nm decrease in particle size, the total quantity of particles (particulate matter) decreased as the nanoparticle blending ratio increased.

Fig 14. Brake power V/S PM

In⁽¹⁴⁾ studied the performance, combustion, and emission reduction characteristics of metal-based silicon dioxide nanoparticle additives included in ternary fuel (Diesel-SMME-iso butanol) on a Diesel engine (TFSi60). The brake thermal efficiency of Diesel, TFSi60, and D80B20 was 30.13%, 34.35%, and 30.14%, respectively. The brake-specific fuel consumption of Diesel, TFSi60, and D80B20 was .28 kg/KW-hr, .279 kg/KW-hr, and .30 kg/KW-hr, respectively. The % age of CO of Diesel, TFSi60, and D80B20 was 0.22 %/vol, 0.2234 %/vol, and 0.14%/vol, respectively. Based on the comparison of research TFSi60 and D80B20+Al₂O₃, it states that the combustion and emission results are similar to those of a Diesel engine. The use of silicon dioxide (without high fuel injection pressure) may deposit on engine walls. The varying fuel injection pressure at 240 bar is that it may take place of complete combustion. The cost of silicon dioxide is more than the aluminum oxide.

4 Conclusion

This study emphasizes the Bio-Diesel blends using Al₂O₃ nanoparticles could be a viable alternative for Diesel. The findings are as follows:

Enhanced Performance with Al₂O₃: Adding 100 mg/L of Al₂O₃ to all Bio-Diesel blends lowers brake-specific fuel consumption while increasing brake mechanical and thermal efficiency. The best performance and emission parameters for Bio-Diesel blends containing Al₂O₃ were found to be achieved with an injection pressure of 240 bar. **Emission Reductions:** Blends of Bio-Diesel containing Al₂O₃ have been shown to have a considerable positive impact on the environment by reducing CO and HC emissions when compared to Diesel. **Blend Optimization:** Lower blends (B10 and B20) provide the best balance of efficiency and emissions, whereas higher blends (B30 and B40) require additional optimization to address viscosity and atomization issues.

An alternate fuel utilized in this investigation was fuel made from iso-butanol nanoparticle Bio-Diesel. **Influence of Injection Pressure:** The results clearly show that 240 bar injection pressure provides the optimum performance and emission characteristics. Increased injection pressures lead to better atomization and spray patterns, which promote more effective combustion. The effects of the Al₂O₃ nano-additive Blends of Bio-Diesel showed improved combustion and emission characteristics when 100 mg/L of Al₂O₃ was added. The enhanced BSFC, lower HC and CO emissions, and increased BTHE were all the outcomes of the catalytic action of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles. **Optimal Blend:** B20+ Al₂O₃ was the most promising fuel substitute for Diesel among the evaluated fuels, providing a fair trade-off between emissions, efficiency, and performance. This blend maintained low emissions and competitive BSFC while achieving exceptional BTHE and MECH values.

- The brake has a 9.96% gain in thermal efficiency. At a fuel injection pressure of 240 bar, the B20 blend's highest biodiesel thermal efficiency was 27.96%.
- As the fuel injection pressure of the engine increases from 180 bar to 240 bar, the mechanical efficiency increases from 43.46 to 52.53% at peak loads.
- Fuel consumption related to the brakes is greatly reduced when injection pressure rises.
- There was a 0.22 to 0.08 percent of volume drop in CO percentage when the direct injection pressure rose from 180 Bar to 240 Bar.
- At 180 bars, the B20 blend has a very low opacity and nil fuel injection pressure.
- The biodiesel blend produced 10–15% fewer PM2.5 and PM10 than pure diesel fuel.

Limitation

In comparison to Diesel, iso-butanol's high energy content raises the combustion temperature, which would lead to a higher production of NO_x (Oxides of Nitrogen).

Future scope

- In order to reduce the excess generation of NO_x (nitrogen oxides), a system of exhaust gas recirculation techniques may be helpful.
- The engine's strength and durability may be improved and carbon sticking may be decreased by applying piston coating.
- High injection pressure may have the potential to reduce particle matter.

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